

An insight into optical rotation of amino-acids[†]

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Abstract : Optical specific rotation of naturally occurring L-amino-acids depend upon physico-chemical properties of amino-acids, solvent used for their preparation and incident radiation. The most important parameters like total polarization, dielectric constant, dipole moment, density and molecular weights of the amino-acids are connected to optical specific rotation by mathematical equations.

The present paper elucidates the variation in specific optical rotation of amino-acids with a few physico-chemical properties namely total unbound electronic charge, molecular weight, furthest distance of substituent group from asymmetric carbon atom, surface area, charge density, molecular volume, solubility and pI values. Probable reasons for these observations have been offered.

Intrinsic conformations of amino-acids and the total polarization with incident low ionizing radiation for amino-acids should lead to measurable changes in specific optical rotation as compared to un-irradiated amino-acids. So long the bonds between asymmetric carbon atom and functional groups do not disrupt upon impingement of low ionizing radiation the variation in optical rotation compared to un-irradiated amino-acid should be obtained. The potential uses of this study in dosimetry and radioprotection are bright.

Keywords : Specific rotation, polarizability, dielectric constant, dipole moment, distortion polarization, inter-relationship with optical rotation, expected changes in specific rotation with low energy radiations, potential uses.

Introduction

Twenty L-amino-acids play a variety of roles through proteins and enzymes¹. Specific optical rotation shown by amino-acids is mostly an intrinsic property that is connected to many physico-chemical properties of these compounds. Cosmic life started by interaction of low energy (e.g. far UV) photon on amino-acids²⁻⁴. So it is worthwhile to probe theoretically into the physico-chemical properties of amino-acids that influence specific optical rotation in the un-irradiated and irradiated states.

Primary concepts of optical rotation :

An optically active sample when placed in a plane polarized light, the electric vector of the light oscillates as :

$$E = i E_0 \sin \omega t \quad (1)$$

where, E = electric vector of plane polarized light; i = unit vector in X -direction and $\omega = 2\pi\nu$ = circular frequency of light.

The light after passing through an optically active sample changes its non-planar ellipticity for maximum amplitude and orientation of ellipse. These are measures of optical activity.

Terminologies and factors influencing optical rotation :

(i) Molar ellipticity : $[\theta] = 1000/CL$ (2)

(ii) Molar rotation : $[\Phi] = 1000 \Phi/CL$ (3)

where, C = concentration of sample in moles per litre; L = path length.

Degree of rotation is proportional to length of active substance traversed. The rotatory power is approximately

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inversely proportional to square of wavelength. Normally D lines of sodium, $\lambda = 5893 \text{ \AA}$ is used. For polypeptides and proteins Drude-Mofitt equation is used. As it is beyond the scope of this article only the relevant equations are being mentioned.

(iii) Drude-Mofitt equation : For random coil polypeptides and denatured proteins outside their wavelength range of absorption obeys Drude equation. This is given by :

$$[m']_{\lambda} = k/(\lambda - \lambda c^2) \quad (4)$$

where k and λc are constants; m' = reduced molar rotation. If a helix component is present, the optical rotatory dispersion curve can be approximated as given by Mofitt⁵.

$$[m']_{\lambda} = a_0 \frac{\lambda_0^2}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2} + b_0 \left(\frac{\lambda_0^2}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2} \right)^2 \quad (5)$$

the slope is obtained as b_0 for resulting straight line. This serves as a measure of helix content. For proteins optical rotation is also dependent upon the refractive index of the solvent n_{λ} at the wavelength λ . This is given by Lorentz equation :

$$[m']_{\lambda}^T = \frac{3}{n\lambda^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{\text{MRW}}{100} \cdot \frac{\alpha}{c \cdot d} \quad (6)$$

[degree.cm²/decimal]

where, MRW = mean residue weight.

Rotatory power increases with temperature. Measurement temperature is 20–25 °C. The degree of rotation is independent of concentration for dilute solutions, but it varies with concentration for concentrated solution. Cations and anions obtained by mixing inorganic salt with optically active acid and base produces optical rotation which is a summation of contribution by these ions towards optical rotation. Rule of shift, rule of optical superposition and distance rule are also some of the primary concepts^{6–9}. Melting points (range 186 to 344 °C), solubilities (range 0.04 to 162 g/100 ml), densities (range 1.2 to 1.8 g/ml) and refractive indices (range 1.1 to 1.8) of amino-acids vary and thereby influence specific optical rotation.

Specific rotation :

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t = \alpha \lambda / L \times d \quad (7)$$

or

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda}^t = \alpha_{\lambda}^t / L \times C \quad (8)$$

where, L = thickness of layer in cm; d = density of liquid; C = number of grammes of substance per ml of solution; α = observed rotation; t = temperature and λ = wavelength of light used.

Molecular rotation :

$$[M]_{\lambda}^t = [\alpha]_{\lambda}^t \times m/100 \quad (9)$$

where, m = molecular weight.

Relationship^{10,11} between dipole moment, dielectric constant and optical rotation of amino-acids :

$$E_m = \text{Maximum amplitude of } E \text{ in eq. (1)} \\ = k_2 P = k_1 [\Phi] \quad (10)$$

and

$$P = \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon - 2} M/d \quad (11)$$

The total polarization P of an amino-acid

$$= P_0 + Pe + Pd \quad (12)$$

where P_0 = orientation polarization, Pe = electronic polarization and Pd = distortion polarization and ϵ = dielectric constant of an amino-acid for a known concentration. M = Molecular weight of amino-acid and D = density of amino-acid. Approximately P is = M/d . Its range has been found to be 61.2 to 155.2.

Now

$$P = (4\pi/3) N.(\mu^2/3kT) + Pd \\ = (4\pi N \mu^2/9kT) + Pd = B/T + Pd \quad (13)$$

where, $B = 4\pi N \mu^2/9k$. Distortion polarization decides the optical rotation of amino-acids in the un-irradiated and irradiated states. As orientation polarization P_0 and total polarization P are experimentally determinable, distortion polarization $Pd = P - P_0$ can be found out. Here, μ = dipole moment, k = Boltzmann's constant; N = Avogadro's number; T = absolute temperature.

Dielectric constant, dipole moment and molecular polarisability^{5,11} :

Average dipole moment along Z axis of all solute molecules can be given by the equation as follows :

$$\langle \mu \rangle = d \Phi \sin \theta_0 \mu \cos \theta_w (\theta) \\ = \mu^2 E_2/3kT \text{ (terms in } E_2)^3 \quad (14)$$

The average dipole moment $\langle \mu \rangle$ will contribute to the overall dielectric constant of the solution. The molecular polarisability,

$$\alpha = \alpha_i + \alpha_d \quad (15)$$

where, α_i = field induced distortion of electron distribution of molecule and possibly also field induced migration of counter-ion and α_d = field induced molecular orientation. An induced dipole moment can be expressed as $\mu = \alpha E$ and field induced molecular orientation,

$$\alpha_d = \mu^2/3kT \quad (16)$$

Mathematical derivation of physico-chemical properties of amino-acids connected with specific rotation :

(i) Surface area : Surface area of an amino acid = πRg^2 . Radius of gyration of an amino-acid,

$$Rg = (Rg^2)^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

where, $Rg^2 = \sum m_i r_i^2 / \sum m_i$, where r_i = distance of sub-unit I with mass m_i from centre of mass in one molecular configuration. For determining Rg for an amino-acid, the centre of mass was chosen from one configuration of an amino-acid and by giving weightage for the atomic weights of different atoms disposed around it. This value is without hydration of amino-acid.

(ii) Molecular volume :

$$\text{Volume of an amino-acid} = 4/3 \pi Rg^3 \quad (18)$$

assuming the amino-acid to be a sphere of average radius Rg .

(iii) Furthest distance(F.D.) of substituent group from

asymmetric carbon atom :

This is the maximum distance of substituent group from asymmetric carbon atom. This has been obtained from algebraic summation of bond distances from asymmetric carbon atom to the substituent group which is placed at a maximum distance in a linear manner.

(iv) Electronic charge (E.C.) :

Total unbound electronic charge has been calculated in electrostatic unit (e.s.u.).

(v) Dielectric constant : The solvent dielectric constant has been taken to be 74 at 20 °C for water. Dielectric constant of an amino-acid solution depends upon (i) concentration of solution, (ii) mole fraction of polar component of a solvent and (iii) frequency of measurement. The variation in dielectric constant with these parameters has been shown (Table 1).

(vi) The solvent dipole moment has been taken to be 1.84 D for water.

$$\text{(vii) Charge density} = \frac{\text{Total unbound electronic charge} \times 10^{-10} \text{ e.s.u.}}{\text{Surface area of amino-acid } (\text{\AA})^2} \quad (19)$$

All other parameters namely molecular weight, solubi-

Table 1. Dielectric constant values of a few amino-acids in aqueous solution⁸

Water-glycine system; Temp. 25 °C									
Glycine									
Concn. of solution (g-equiv/L)	0.0	0.25	0.50	1.50	2.0	2.5			
Dielectric constant	81.0	86.84	92.39	115.10	126.50	138.30			
Water-alanine system; Temp. 18 °C; Frequency = 0.9 MHz									
Water- α -alanine					Water- β -alanine				
Mole fraction of polar component	100	75	50	25	0	50	20	10	0
Dielectric constant	103.8	98.08	92.64	86.51	81.0	102.1	88.8	85.1	81.0
Water-proline system; Temp. 20 °C; Concn. : 1 g-equiv/L; pH 6.5									
Variation of dielectric constant with frequency									
Frequency (MHz)	Real part of dielectric constant (ϵ')					Imaginary part of dielectric constant (ϵ'')			
300	100.1					6.4			
600	99.5					11.8			
900	96.4					15.7			
1200	96.3					19.3			
1500	91.5					21.6			
1800	87.3					23.2			
2000	64.4					24.3			

lity, pI etc. were used for giving the different Tables. These have been obtained from published literature.

Results

Influence of eight physico-chemical factors on $[\alpha]$ has been shown in Tables 2 to 9.

(a) *Electronic charge* : Variation in the degree of specific rotation and their signs with variation of electronic charges have been shown in Table 2 (Part 1 to Part 4). For a fixed charge of 48×10^{-10} e.s.u. from leucine to alanine the $[\alpha]$ value has changed from positive to negative and its intensity is increased (Part 1). For fixed charge

Table 2. Variation in the degree of specific rotation and their signs with variation of electronic charges for amino-acids

Amino-acids	Electronic charge $\times 10^{-10}$ e.s.u.	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Leu	48	+11.10°	Linear decrease in specific rotation for same electronic charge, sign reversal and increase in magnitude of rotation
Val	48	-6.11°	
Met	48	-10.00°	
Ala	48	-19.50°	
Part 2			
Lysine	57.5	+14.60°	Linear decrease in positive specific rotation for same electronic charge
Arg	57.5	+11.37°	
Glu	57.5	+8.00°	
Part 3			
Ser	67.2	+6.87°	Linear decrease of positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal in specific rotation and its increase for same electronic charge
His	67.2	+5.40°	
Asp	67.2	+4.36°	
Thr	67.2	-4.00°	
Tyr	67.2	-15.50°	
Part 4			
Leu	48.0	+11.10°	Linear decrease in positive specific rotation with increase in electronic charge
Glu	57.5	+8.00°	
His	67.2	+5.40°	

Table 3. Variation in the degree of specific rotation and their signs with variation in molecular weight of amino-acids

Amino-acids	Molecular weight	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Lys	146.18	+14.60°	Within a very small variation in molecular weight decrease in value followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation
Gln	147.13	+8.00°	
Glu	147.13	-1.80°	
Met	149.21	-10.00°	
Part 2			
Lys	146.18	+14.60°	Decrease in degree followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation with decrease in molecular weight
Asn	132.11	+5.40°	
Thr	119.12	-4.00°	
Val	117.14	-6.11°	
Ala	89.09	-19.50°	
Part 3			
Arg	74.20	+11.37°	Decrease in degree of specific rotation with increase in molecular weight
His	115.15	+5.40°	

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Table 4. Variation in degree of specific rotation as a function of furthest distance (F.D.) of substituent group from asymmetric carbon atom for amino-acids

Amino-acids	Furthest distance (F.D.) (Å)	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Ser	3.08	+6.87°	For same F.D. linear decrease and sign reversal in degree of specific rotation and its increase
Thr	3.08	-4.00°	
Val	3.08	-6.11°	
Ala	3.08	-19.50°	
Part 2			
Leu	4.62	+11.10°	For same F.D. linear decrease in degree of positive specific rotation
Asn	4.62	+5.40°	
Asp	4.62	+4.36°	
Part 3			
Gln	6.16	+8.00°	For same F.D. decrease in degree of positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation
His	6.16	+5.40°	
Glu	6.16	-1.80°	
Met	6.16	-10.00°	
Part 4			
Lys	7.70	+14.60°	With decrease in F.D. decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation
Gln	6.16	+8.00°	
Asp	4.62	+4.36°	
Thr	3.08	-4.00°	
Val	3.08	-6.11°	

Table 5. Variation in degree of specific rotation as a function of surface area of amino-acids

Amino-acids	Surface area (Å) ²	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Phe	29.82	+71.00°	Sharp linear decrease in positive specific rotation followed by negative specific rotation with decrease in surface area
Leu	16.79	+11.10°	
Val	7.05	-6.11°	
Part 2			
Val	7.45	-6.11°	Increase in negative specific rotation with increase in surface area
Met	29.80	-10.00°	
Part 3			
Ala	7.45	-19.50°	Increase in negative specific rotation with increase in surface area
Ilu	16.77	-25.50°	
Part 4			
Ser	7.45	+6.87°	No regularity in increase of specific rotation with increase in surface area
Asp	16.77	+4.36°	
Gln	29.82	+8.00°	
Part 5			
Asp	16.77	+4.36°	Increase in positive specific rotation followed by plateau with increase in surface area
His	29.82	+5.40°	
Lys	46.59	+14.60°	
Arg	67.09	+11.37°	

Table 6. Variation in degree of specific rotation as a function of charge density of amino-acids

Amino-acids	Charge density [(e.s.u.)/(Å) ² × 10 ⁻¹⁰]	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Lys	1.24	+14.60°	With a linear increase in charge density there is a decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal of specific rotation
Leu	2.86	+11.10°	
Asn	4.58	+5.41°	
Thr	8.45	-4.00°	
Part 2			
Arg	0.86	+11.37°	With a linear increase in charge density there is a linear decrease of positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal of specific rotation
Gln	1.93	+8.00°	
Val	6.44	-6.11°	
Part 3			
Gln	1.93	+8.00°	With increase in charge density there is a linear decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal of specific rotation
His	1.92	+5.40°	
Ala	6.44	-19.50°	
Part 4			
Met	1.61	-10.00°	With linear increase in charge density there is linear increase in negative specific rotation
Tyr	1.95	-15.80°	
Ileu	2.86	-25.50°	
Part 5			
Met	1.61	-10.00°	With linear increase in charge density there is a linear increase in specific rotation from negative value to positive
Glu	2.90	-1.80°	
Asp	4.01	+4.36°	
Asn	4.58	+5.40°	
Cys	9.02	+25.50°	

Table 7. Variation in specific rotation of amino-acids as a function of molecular volume of amino-acids

Amino-acids	Molecular volume (Å) ³	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Cys	15.31	+25.50°	Linear decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal for fixed molecular volume
Ser	15.31	+6.87°	
Val	15.31	+6.11°	
Ala	15.31	-19.50°	
Part 2			
Leu	51.65	+11.10°	Linear decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal for fixed molecular volume
Asn	51.65	+5.40°	
Asp	51.65	+4.36°	
Ileu	51.65	-25.50°	

Part 3			
Gln	122.44	+8.44°	Linear decrease in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation for fixed molecular volume
His	122.44	+5.40°	
Glu	122.44	-1.80°	
Met	122.44	-10.00°	

Table 8. Variation of specific rotation as a function of solubility of amino-acids

Amino-acids	Solubility (g/100 ml)	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Try	1.14	+33.00°	Fast decrease in positive specific rotation, followed by sign reversal and increase in negative specific rotation with change in solubility
Leu	2.00	+11.10°	
Ser	25.00	+6.87°	
Val	9.00	-6.11°	
Ala	10.05	-19.50°	
Part 2			
His	0.40	+5.40°	Average increase in positive specific rotation followed by sign reversal and fast increase in negative specific rotation with change in solubility
Asp	0.82	+4.36°	
Gln	4.25	+8.00°	
Met	3.00	-10.00°	
Ileu	4.00	-25.50°	
Part 3			
Asp	0.82	+4.36°	A linear increase in positive specific rotation with change in solubility
Asn	0.40	+5.40°	
Ser	25.00	+6.87°	
Glu	4.25	+8.00°	

Table 9. Variation in specific rotation as a function of pI values of amino-acids

Amino-acids	pI Value	Specific rotation	Feature
Part 1			
Cys	5.11	+25.50°	For a slight change in pI value (range 5.11-6.04) the positive $[\alpha]$ value decreases, then sign reversal occurs and negative specific rotation increases
Gln	5.70	+8.00°	
Ser	5.68	+6.87°	
Asn	5.41	+5.40°	
Thr	5.60	-4.00°	
Val	6.00	-6.11°	
Tyr	5.66	-15.80°	
Ileu	6.04	-25.50°	
Part 2			
Glu	3.08	-1.80°	With increase in pI value there is sign reversal and increase in $[\alpha]$ value
His	7.64	+5.40°	
Arg	10.76	+11.37°	

Part 3			
Asp	2.98	+4.36°	With increase in pI value there is linear increase in positive $[\alpha]$ value
Gln	5.70	+8.00°	
Lys	9.74	+14.60°	
Part 3			
Pro	2.98	+4.36°	With increase in pI value increase in positive specific rotation
Gln	5.70	+8.00°	
Lys	9.74	+14.60°	

of 57.5×10^{-10} e.s.u. from lysine to glutamine a steady decrease in positive $[\alpha]$ value has been observed (Part 2). For a fixed charge of 67.2×10^{-10} e.s.u. from serine to tyrosine a steady decrease in positive $[\alpha]$ value followed by sign reversal and increase in magnitude of negative $[\alpha]$ value has been observed (Part 3). With increase in charge from 48 to 67.2×10^{-10} e.s.u. a steady decrease in positive $[\alpha]$ value has been observed from leucine to histidine (Part 4).

(b) *Molecular weight* : Variation in the degree of specific rotation and their signs with variation in molecular weight of amino-acids have been shown in Table 3 (Part 1 to Part 3). For a small change in molecular weight (from 146.18 to 149.21) a decrease in positive $[\alpha]$ value followed by sign reversal and increase in negative $[\alpha]$ value has been observed from lysine to methionine (Part 1). As the value of molecular weight has consistently decreased from 146.18 to 89.09 from lysine to alanine the positive $[\alpha]$ decreases followed by sign reversal and subsequent increase in negative $[\alpha]$ value (Part 2). Again when there is an increase in molecular weight from 74.20 to 115.15 for arginine to histidine a decrease in positive $[\alpha]$ value has been observed (Part 3).

(c) *Furthest distance (F.D.) of substituent group from asymmetric carbon atom* :

(i) F.D. = 3.08 Å : The $[\alpha]$ values change from a positive value of +6.87 to -19.5° from serine to alanine in a linear manner (Part 1, Table 4).

(ii) F.D. = 4.62 Å : The $[\alpha]$ values decrease from +11.1 to +4.36° for leucine to aspartic acid linearly (Part 2, Table 4).

(iii) F.D. = 6.16 Å : The $[\alpha]$ values change from +8° for glutamine to -10° for methionine linearly (Part 3, Table 4).

(iv) With decrease in F.D. from 7.70 Å for lysine to 3.08 Å for valine, a consistent decrease in positive $[\alpha]$

value followed by sign reversal and increase in negative $[\alpha]$ value has been observed (Part 4, Table 4).

(d) *Surface area* : (i) With increase in surface area from $7.5 (\text{Å})^2$ to $29.82 (\text{Å})^2$ for valine to phenylalanine the $[\alpha]$ value changes from -6.11 to +71° linearly (Part 1, Table 5). (ii) Again with increase in surface area from $7.45 (\text{Å})^2$ to $29.8 (\text{Å})^2$ the $[\alpha]$ value changes from -6.11 to -10.0° for valine and methionine (Part 2, Table 5). (iii) Similarly with increase in surface area from $7.45 (\text{Å})^2$ to $16.77 (\text{Å})^2$ the $[\alpha]$ value changes from -19.5 to -25.5° for alanine and isoleucine (Part 3, Table 5). (iv) With increase in surface area from $7.45 (\text{Å})^2$ for serine to $29.82 (\text{Å})^2$ for glutamine, the $[\alpha]$ values decrease from +6.87 to +4.36° and again increase to +8.00° (Part 4, Table 5). (v) For aspartic acid, histidine, lysine and arginine as the surface area increases from $16.77 (\text{Å})^2$ to $67.09 (\text{Å})^2$ the $[\alpha]$ values change from +4.36 to +11.37° non-linearly (Part 5, Table 5).

(e) *Molecular volume* : Three different straight lines have been obtained for three molecular volumes of $15.31 (\text{Å})^3$, $51.65 (\text{Å})^3$ and $122.44 (\text{Å})^3$ for (i) alanine to cysteine, the $[\alpha]$ values changing from -19.5 to +25.5° (Part 1), (ii) isoleucine to leucine, the $[\alpha]$ values changing from -25.5 to +11.1° (Part 2) and (iii) methionine to glutamine, the $[\alpha]$ values changing from -10 to +8° (Part 3). All are in Table 6.

(f) *Solubility* : The $[\alpha]$ values change from +33 to -19.5° for an increase in solubility from 1 to 17 g/100 ml in a parabolic manner (Part 1, Table 7) for tryptophan to alanine. But $[\alpha]$ values change from +5.4 to -25.5° for histidine to isoleucine having their solubilities changing from 0.4 to 4 g/100 ml (Part 2, Table 7). Again $[\alpha]$ values increase with increase in solubility for aspartic acid to glutamine (Part 3, Table 7).

The amino-acids can be arranged in the decreasing order of solubility¹² as : Pro > Thr > Cys > Lys > Gly > Ala > Arg > Val > Ileu > Gln > Met > = Ser = Phe > Asn > Leu > Try > Glu > Asp = His > Tyr.

(g) *pI* : For the *pI* range of 5.11 to 6.04, the $[\alpha]$ values change linearly from +25.5 to -25.5° for nine amino-acids from cysteine to isoleucine (Part 1, Table 8). With increase in *pI* value from 3.08 to 10.76 the $[\alpha]$ value changes linearly from -1.8 to +11.37° for glutamine to arginine (Part 2, Table 8). With increase in *pI* values from 2.98 to 9.74 the $[\alpha]$ values increased linearly from aspartic acid to lysine (Part 3, Table 8).

(h) *Charge density* (ρ_c) : (i) As charge density increases for lysine to threonine from 1.2 to 9.0×10^{-10} e.s.u./(\AA)² the $[\alpha]$ value linearly decreases from +14.6 to -4.0° (Part 1, Table 9). (ii) With increase in charge density from 0.9 to 6.5×10^{-10} e.s.u./(\AA)² for arginine to valine, the $[\alpha]$ value decreases from +11.37 to -6.11° linearly (Part 2, Table 9). (iii) Again with increase in charge density, from 0.9 to 6.5×10^{-10} e.s.u./(\AA)² for arginine to alanine the $[\alpha]$ value decreases from +11.37 to -19.5° linearly (Part 3, Table 9). (iv) With increase in charge density from 1.6 to 2.9×10^{-10} e.s.u./(\AA)², the negative value of $[\alpha]$ increases linearly (Part 4, Table 9). (v) With increase in charge density from 1.6 to 9.0×10^{-10} e.s.u./(\AA)² for methionine to cysteine, the $[\alpha]$ value changes from -10 to +25.5° linearly (Part 5, Table 9).

Discussion

In all three parts, in general, $[\alpha]$ values have changed with change in molecular weight (Parts 1, 2 and 3). But when the electronic charges have increased (Parts 1 to 3), the $[\alpha]$ values have been decreased. Same trend has been observed in Part 4 also. So, polarization and accordingly $[\alpha]$ value is dependent upon both electronic charge and molecular weight (Table 2).

In Parts 1 and 2, either for same molecular weight range or decrease in molecular weight, decrease in polarization has led to lower values of specific rotation. But in Part 3 opposite trend has been observed. Here polarization is dependent upon charge distribution, which is more for Arg compared to His (Table 3).

A charge bearing substituent group will produce in-

ductive effect when it is 2-3 carbon atoms away from asymmetric carbon atom, thereby influencing polarisation. Arg, Lys, Gln, His, Glu, Asn, Asp, Thr and Ser are hydrophilic but Val, Ala, Met and Leu are hydrophobic. Polarization is a complex phenomenon where inductive effect, hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity and dipole moment influence it. This has been reflected in Table 4.

In general with increase in surface area the extent of specific rotation (either positive or negative) has increased. Now, polarization is approximately equal to M/d . The calculated polarization values have increased from 95.2 for Val to 155 for Phe (Part 1) and 66.19 for Asp to 145.2 for Arg (Part 5). With increase in polarization specific rotation has also increased. The non-polar side chains as in Val, Met, Ileu, Leu, Phe will not alter the polarization in the same manner as polar side chains in Lys, Arg, His, Asp or Ser (Table 5).

In Parts 1 to 4 there is a decrease and reversal in sign of specific rotation for amino-acids with increase in charge density. In fact in all these figures M/d values have also consistently decreased in the same sequence as the $[\alpha]$ values. So with decrease of polarization specific optical rotation have also decreased. In Part 5 there is a variability in M/d values. The non-bonded electrons in Cys and Met contributes to high polarization leading to high $[\alpha]$ values (Table 6).

It will be observed that with increase in molecular volume there is a general tendency to decrease in specific optical rotation (Parts 1, 2 and 3). Polarization becomes easier with small molecular volume but difficult with high molecular volume (Table 7).

Solubility alone only indicates the hydrophilic character of the amino-acids. It has got very little to do with specific rotation alone (Table 8).

pI value of an amino-acid is an indication of total balancing of net positive and negative charges. But here it appears that more of chromophoricity is connected to the increased value of specific rotation whose *pI* values are more than 7.0 e.g. His, Lys and Arg (Parts 2 and 3). From Cys to Ileu (Part 1) there is variation in M/d values, chromophoricity and total unbound charge. All these have contributed to variation in specific optical rotation values (Table 9).

Optical rotation of amino-acids and radiation :

Effect of UV radiation : In the wavelength range from 200 nm up to 380 nm, amount of energy per quantum for Avogadro number of molecules of amino-acids = $Nh\nu = Nhc/\lambda$, where $N = 6.623 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$; $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34} \text{ JS}$ and $c = 3 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm/s}$. Ultra-violet radiation is expected to influence distortion polarization in the amino-acids. This will change the specific rotation of amino-acids.

Effect of X-rays or gamma-rays : For X-ray or gamma-rays the total dose, dose rate, LET of radiation etc. are determining factors for causing a change in distortion polarization (Pd) of amino-acid molecules. So, specific rotation will be different compared to un-irradiated amino-acids.

The different possibilities are given below :

(i) If total dose is more than bond energy by which the different groups are connected to the asymmetric carbon atom, the bonds will be broken. So optical rotation will not be obtained.

(ii) If dose rate is small (i.e. 0.4 to 2 Gy/min)¹³, energy transduction through the bonds of the amino-acids will take place thereby altering charge density around asymmetric carbon atom. This will alter the angle of rotation of amino-acids depending upon absorbed radiation dose and bond energy. The bond energy between asymmetric carbon atom and connecting functional groups present in amino-acids have been given in Table 10.

Table 10. The bond energies between asymmetric carbon atom and connecting functional groups present in amino-acids¹⁸

Asymmetric carbon atom connected with a functional group	Bond energy (kcal/mol)
C-H	98.8
C-C	83.1
C-SH	62.0
C-OH	84.0
C-CH ₂	83.1
C-NH ₂	69.7
C-COOH	83.1
C-CONH	83.1
C-S	62.0

Futuristic potential practical utility :**(i) Dosimetric application :**

If the specific rotation of an amino-acid is propor-

tional to dose of radiation under fixed experimental parameters like concentration, pH, ionic strength, etc. then this property can be used for dosimetric purposes within the linear range of dose-response relationship. Moreover, the amino-acids have been used as dosimetric materials as these are tissue-equivalent. Most of the amino-acids have been used as lyo-luminescence dosimeters¹⁴. Even if the dose-response relationship is not found linear but a linear quadratic relationship is found that can also be used for dosimetric purposes. The amino-group will be first depleted when the dose increases after which it is the - carboxylic acid group as the bond energies are 69.7 and 83.1 kcal/mol respectively (Table 2). So up to a lower dose before it reaches 69.7 kcal/mol bond energy, there will be variation in the distortion polarization (Pd) compared to un-irradiated amino-acid. This variation in Pd is expected to be proportional to dose. It needs to be worked out in details.

(ii) Application in radioprotection :

Amino-acids are known to provide chemical radioprotection when incorporated in experimental animals before irradiation¹⁵. But if amino-acids are irradiated initially and then incorporated in experimental animals their radioprotective efficacy will be severely altered. As optical rotation is likely to change with dose of irradiation it is possible to ascertain the dose up to which an irradiated amino-acid can provide radioprotection. It has been observed by us that while 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan gives radioprotection, the DL variety of this amino-acid gives almost negligible radioprotection. Radioprotection has been demonstrated to be dependent upon configuration of amino-acids like β -mercaptopyrionyl glycine¹⁶ and diltiazem¹⁷.

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Abbreviations used :

M.W. : Molecular weight

Mol. vol. : Molecular volume in (\AA)³

F.D. (\AA) : Furthest distance of substituent groups from asymmetric carbon atom in Angstrom unit (\AA)

E.C. : Total unbound electronic charge in electrostatic unit (e.s.u. $\times 10^{-10}$)

pI : Isoionic pH

$[\alpha]_D^{20}$: Specific rotation

Surface area : in $(\text{Å})^2$

Amino-acids : Asp - aspartic acid; Lys - lysine; Arg - arginine; Asn - asparagine; Leu - leucine; Val - valine; Try - tryptophan; Pro - proline; Cys - cysteine; Ileu - isoleucine; Met - methionine; Ser - serine; Glu - glutamine; Phe - phenylalanine; Ala - alanine; Tyr - tyrosine; Thr - threonine; His - histidine; Glu - glutamic acid

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